

An empirical study on the status quo and influencing factors of College students' sense of gain from ideological and political theory courses ——Taking the Conspectus of Chinese Modern History course as an example

Lu Liqing¹, Wan Qiumeng²

¹School of Marxism, Zhejiang Gongshang University.

²Zhejiang Gongshang University.

Abstract: Taking the Conspectus of Chinese Modern History Course as an example, this study adopts the method of empirical research to explore the status quo and influencing factors of College students' sense of gain from ideological and political theory courses. A sample of 831 undergraduate students in school has carried on the questionnaire survey, the difference comparison, multiple regression, structural equation model analysis are used for data analysis, and the results show that college students' overall sense of gain from the Conspectus of Chinese Modern History Course is good, and there is no significant difference in gender and nationality, but there is a significant difference in major. Social support, family rendering and school teaching have a significant impact on college students' sense of gain in the Conspectus of Chinese Modern History Course. According to the research results, a series of Suggestions are provided on how to improve college students' sense of gain from the Conspectus of Chinese Modern History Course.

Key words: Sense of gain from the Conspectus of Chinese Modern History Course; The status quo. Influencing factors; Countermeasures and Suggestions

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***Corresponding author:** LU Liqing, 270281149@qq.com

I. Research background

From 7th to 8th in December, 2016, President Xi said

at the National Conference on Ideological and political work in colleges and universities: "To do a good job in ideological and political work in colleges and universities, we must adapt to events, advance with the time, and innovate according to the situation. We should make good use of classroom teaching as the main channel, strengthening the ideological and political theory course in the process of improvement, enhancing the affinity and pertinence of ideological and political education, and meeting the needs and expectations of students' growth and development."ⁱⁱ What President Xi Jinping said pointed out the development direction for the construction of ideological and political theory course in the new era. In order to thoroughly implement the spirit of the national college ideological and political work conference, in May 2017, the leading party group of the ministry of education, PRC deliberated and approved the general plan for the special work on the teaching quality of ideological and political theory courses in colleges and universities in 2017, which clearly pointed out that "it aims to fight a tough battle to improve the quality and level of ideological and political theory courses in colleges and universities, and effectively enhance the sense of gain from ideological and political theory courses among college students."ⁱⁱⁱ College students' sense of gain from ideological and political theory courses is the product of the new situation faced by the ideological and political theory courses in the new era. It undertakes the task of evaluating whether the ideological and political theory courses in universities have affinity and pertinence, the

degree of affinity and pertinence, and whether the ideological and political theory courses meet the needs and expectations of students' growth and development. Therefore, to clarify the concept of college students' sense of gain from ideological and political theory courses, to develop a tool for measuring college students' sense of gain from ideological and political theory courses, to analyze the influence factors of college students' sense of gain from ideological and political theory courses are of great significance to improve the teaching quality and teaching methods of ideological and political theory course in colleges and universities.

The Conspectus of Chinese Modern History Course as the important curriculum of the undergraduate course of ideological and political theory courses in colleges and universities, which is from the perspective of history, to help Chinese college students understand "It is the history of China and the Chinese people chose the communist party of China, selected marxism and the socialist road, selected the historical inevitability of reform and opening up, enhance the confidence of the construction of the socialist cause with Chinese characteristics."^[1]

This study selects the Conspectus of Chinese Modern History Course as the representative course of ideological and political theory course in colleges and universities, and through questionnaire survey, adopts the methods of difference comparison, multiple regression, and structural equation model analysis to discuss the status quo and main influencing factors of college students' sense of gain from the Conspectus of Chinese Modern History Course and puts forward some suggestions on how to cultivate and enhance college students' sense of gain from ideological and political theory courses.

II. Literature review and research hypothesis

1. literature review

As for the specific meaning of college students' sense of gain from ideological and political courses, one point of view holds that college students' sense of gain from ideological and political courses is that college students feel that ideological and political courses are courses that can be learned and used.^[2] According to this view, college students' sense of gain from ideological and political courses is equal to their satisfaction with ideological and political courses, that is, whether they are satisfied with the teaching of ideological and political courses or not. The ultimate goal is to realize the change of students' attitude towards ideological and political courses from "passive learning" to "active learning".^[3] Another point of view holds that college students' sense of gain from ideological and political courses refers to the positive, continuous and real psychological feelings generated by the "acquisition" of ideological and political courses after they meet the actual or potential development needs and expectations of college students.^[4] In this view, the essence of college students' sense of gain from ideological and political courses is a positive subjective feeling, which comes from the harvest in the teaching process of ideological and political courses, and the task is to evaluate whether ideological and political courses meet the needs and expectations of students' growth and development. In addition, it is added that the sense of acquisition of college students' ideological and political courses is closely related to the content of moral education, and that the specific connotation of the sense of gain from college students' ideological and political courses is reflected in the enhancement and improvement of students' moral cognition, moral emotion and moral behavior.^[5] This paper holds that college students' sense of gain from ideological and political courses refers to the positive experience and behavioral change caused by college students' participation in the teaching process of ideological and political courses, and its specific connotation includes knowledge mastery, emotional motivation and behavioral guidance. Accordingly, college students' sense of gain from the Conspectus of

Chinese Modern History course specifically refers to the positive experience and behavior change caused by college students' participation in the process of the Conspectus of Chinese Modern History course.

On the analysis of the influencing factors of college students' sense of gain from ideological and political theory courses, most of the existing researches start from the teaching of ideological and political theory courses, and the specific influencing factors include teaching contents, teaching methods and so on. The disconnection between the teaching content and the actual situation of college students is an important aspect that affects the students' sense of gain from ideological and political courses. For example, Yan Guohua proposed that some teaching contents are not closely related to social life, on the one hand, the teaching contents of ideological and political courses tend to be inclined to the value orientation of a higher position, on the other hand, the teaching content is subject to the teachers' teaching thoughts. Teachers tend to bring academic thinking and academic discourse into the classroom, which makes it difficult for college students to accept the teaching content and affects their sense of gain. [6] Zhang Yi pointed out that there is a contradiction between the teaching content and the students' needs. Some of the teaching content did not pay enough attention to the actual confusion of college students and did not have enough ability to examine the real problems, which would separate the real life from the classroom teaching. [7] Liu Jian-jun found that the same content in the current ideological and political courses appeared repeatedly in different learning sections and different courses, [8] which is also inconsistent with the actual needs of students. The improvement and creation of teaching methods have been paid great attention in the field of ideological and political teaching all the time. In recent years, a variety of new teaching methods have emerged, such as flipped classroom, online and offline hybrid teaching and so on. The new teaching method, which has been rapidly popularized, has injected new vitality into the teaching of ideological and political

courses, and to some extent has improved the participation and college students' sense of gain from ideological and political courses. However, some problems are exposed in the process of applying the new teaching method. Such as the fragmentation of knowledge taught in the classroom, the difficulty in controlling students' attention, the difficulty in selecting massive learning resources, etc. [9] It weakens college students' sense of gain from knowledge in the actual learning process. Teachers' language expression directly affects students' reception and acceptance of knowledge, thus affecting students' sense of gain. Explain the profound marxist theory with the words that students understand and like to hear, [10] is the ideal effect of ideological and political theory teaching. [11] At present, college students' ideological and political education discourse on the expression of "fracture" and "fragmentation". Subjectively, some teachers of ideological and political courses lack the willingness to innovate in online discourse, fail to keep up with the trend and pace of The Times, and stick to the one-way communication mode of traditional classroom, which has a declining appeal to college students. [12]

Based on the above views, this study explains the sense of gain from three dimensions: knowledge mastery, emotional motivation and action orientation. By referring to the environmental theory of ideological and political education, the main factors affecting the students' sense of gain from ideological and political theory courses are summarized as social support, family rendering, school teaching. The specific path model is shown in figure 1.

figure 1 path model

2. research hypotheses

2.1 Social support

The influence of social environment on people includes economy, politics, culture and so on. Marxism holds that man is a person living in the society and a person is the sum of all kinds of social relations. People can't live without society. ^[13] Society is bound to have an impact on people's ideas. Since the 18th congress of the communist party of China, China has made historic achievements in reform, opening up and socialist modernization. ^[14] This series of achievements demonstrated the superiority of China's socialist system, the correctness of the Chinese people's choice and adherence to the leadership of the communist party of China, and the authenticity of the content of the Conspectus of Chinese Modern History course. Social support has an invisible influence on college students' sense of gain from the Conspectus of Chinese Modern History course.

Hypothesis (1) : there is a positive correlation between social support and college students' sense of gain from the Conspectus of Chinese Modern History Course.

2.2 Family rendering

Family is the group in which a person lives the earliest and longest. The initial socialization of an individual cannot be separated from family, and the continuation of socialization cannot be separated from family. ^[14] The ideological and moral quality of parents and their educational concept and attitude have a subtle influence on the children's cognition and view of college students' ideological and political theory courses. Such as parents to patriotism consciousness, whether support the leadership of the party and so on will have a certain impact on children's ideology. This research points out that family rendering refers to the influence of the family on children, especially the support of the communist party of China and the strengthening of patriotic education.

Hypothesis (2) : there is a positive correlation between family rendering and college students' sense of gain from the

Conspectus of Chinese Modern History course.

2.3 School teaching

School is a special social organization, is a purposeful, planned, organized to the educatees to impart cultural knowledge, labor skills, values, political views, social norms, in order to train qualified social citizens, so as to the formation of people's ideological and moral character more guidance. ^[14] The influence of school teaching on college students' sense of gain from the Conspectus of Chinese Modern History Course ,that teachers use appropriate teaching methods and educational carriers to teach students the contents of the Conspectus of Chinese Modern History Course with a good teaching attitude and make students have a sense of gain.

Hypothesis (3) : school teaching has a positive impact on college students' sense of gain of the Conspectus of Chinese Modern History Course.

III. Research methods

1. research object

In this study, undergraduates from a provincial university in Zhejiang province are selected as test subjects to study the Conspectus of Chinese Modern History Course in this semester voluntarily. The online and offline questionnaire survey method is adopted. The researcher read out instructions in the classroom, and guided the test subjects to scan the qr code to enter the questionnaire page, and then completed the questionnaire online. A total of 831 valid questionnaires are collected. There are 231 male students and 600 female students in the sample. There are 733 han and 58 ethnic minorities. There are 134 students majoring in literature and history, 57 students majoring in science and technology, 594 students majoring in economics and management, and 48 students majoring in art.

2 .research tools

2.1 College students' sense of gain from the Conspectus of Chinese Modern History Course is measured by a self-designed questionnaire.

On the basis of literature analysis, expert consultation and semi-structured interviews with students, the initial scale of college students' sense of gain from the Conspectus of Chinese Modern History Course is formed. The reliability and validity of the initial scale are tested by item analysis, exploratory factor analysis and reliability analysis, and the final formal scale consisted of three dimensions: knowledge mastery, emotion motivation and will behavior orientation. To construct validity test scale validity, three common factors are extracted by principal component analysis extraction in factor analysis. The variance of the combined interpretation of the three factor constructs is 70.177%, more than 60%, indicating that the three factors retained for extraction had good construction validity. In the reliability test, the internal consistency coefficient of the total scale is 0.953, and the internal consistency coefficient of each factor is 0.919, 0.891 and 0.926, respectively. The data showed that the scale had a high internal consistency and a good reliability.

2.2 The factors affecting college students' sense of gain in the Conspectus of Chinese Modern History Course are measured by a self-designed questionnaire, which is divided into three one-dimensional scales: social support, family rendering and school teaching.

The establishment of the questionnaire content is mainly based on the previous research findings and the analysis of the qualitative interview results in the questionnaire preparation process. According to the results of project analysis, 7 questions are reserved for school teaching, 7 questions are reserved for family rendering and 8 questions are reserved for social support scale. In the exploratory factor analysis, the explanatory variables are 78.726%, 64.175% and

59.519%, respectively, indicating good construction validity. In the reliability test, the internal consistency coefficients of the four scales are 0.955, 0.905 and 0.874, respectively.

3 data processing

SPSS20.0 and AMOS20.0 are used for data analysis. Descriptive statistics are used to analyze the status quo of college students' sense of gain from the Conspectus of Chinese Modern History Course. The independent sample T test and one-way analysis of variance are used to compare the differences in the demographic variables of college students' sense of gain from the Conspectus of Chinese Modern History Course. Multiple linear regression is used to study the path relationship between variables and the structural?

IV. Research findings

equation is used to verify it.

1. analysis of the status quo of college students' sense of gain from the Conspectus of Chinese Modern History Course

1.1 The overall situation of college students' sense of gain from the Conspectus of Chinese Modern History Course

The data in table 1 shows that college students scored highly for their sense of gain from the Conspectus of Chinese Modern History Course. The mean value of the overall sense of achievement is 4.547 (the questionnaire questions are graded from 0 to 5, and the scores of individual questions range from 0 to 5). In the three dimensions of sense of acquisition, the average score of action orientation is the highest, followed by emotional motivation, and the score of knowledge mastery is the lowest.

Table 1 overall situation of college students' sense of gain from the Conspectus of Chinese Modern History Course

	Knowledge mastery	emotional motivation	behavioral guidance	Overall sense of gain
Mean	4.450	4.595	4.612	4.547
Standard Deviation	0.597	0.527	0.536	0.495

1.2 The group difference of college students' sense of gain from the Conspectus of Chinese Modern History Course

1.2.1 gender difference

As can be seen from the data in table 2, although male scored higher than female on knowledge mastery, emotional arousal, action orientation and overall sense of gain, the t statistics of gender variables in the four dependent variables test did not reach the significant level. It shows that there is no significant difference between the students of different genders in the overall sense of gain and the three dimensions of the Conspectus of Chinese Modern History Course.

Table 2 gender differences of college students' sense of gain from the Conspectus of Chinese Modern History Course

Variable	gender	number	mean	Standard Deviation	t
knowledge mastery	male	231	4.505	0.572	1.666 n.s.
	female	600	4.428	0.605	
emotional motivation	male	231	4.608	0.498	0.447 n.s.
	female	600	4.590	0.538	
behavioral guidance	male	231	4.640	0.513	0.916 n.s.
	female	600	4.601	0.544	
Overall Sense of gain	male	231	4.580	0.472	1.203 n.s.
	female	600	4.534	0.503	

n.s. p>0.05

1.2.2 ethnic differences

Again, the data in table 3 shows that the t statistics of the national variables of college students in the four dependent variables of knowledge mastery, emotional motivation, intention and action orientation and overall sense of acquisition also did not reach a significant level, the ethnic difference of college students' sense of gain from the Conspectus of Chinese Modern History Course is still not obvious.

Table 3 ethnic differences of college students' sense of gain from the Conspectus of Chinese Modern History Course

Variable	ethnicity	number	mean	Standard Deviation	t
knowledge mastery	han	733	4.449	0.594	-0.079 n.s.
	Ethnic minorities	58	4.456	0.634	
emotional motivation	han	733	4.591	0.533	-0.685 n.s.
	Ethnic minorities	58	4.641	0.433	
behavioral guidance	han	733	4.608	0.535	-0.840 n.s.
	Ethnic minorities	58	4.670	0.550	
Overall Sense of gain	han	733	4.544	0.499	-0.552 n.s.
	Ethnic minorities	58	4.582	0.436	

1.2.3 professional differences

The difference of college students' sense of gain from the Conspectus of Chinese Modern History Course in demographic variables reflects the major difference. From the data of the analysis of variance in table 4, we found four dependent variables of "knowledge mastery", "emotional motivation", "intention and action orientation" and "overall sense of gain". The F values of the overall test are 3.089, 2.647*, 1.494 n.s. and 2.843*, respectively. Among them, "knowledge mastery", "emotional motivation" and "overall sense of acquisition" all reached significant levels, indicating that college students of different majors had significant differences in "knowledge mastery", "emotional motivation" and "overall sense of acquisition". Therefore, further LSD post-test shows that the scores of students majoring in science and technology on "knowledge mastery", "emotional motivation" and "overall sense of gain" are significantly lower than those of students majoring in literature and history, economics and management, and art.

Table 4 major differences of college students' sense of gain from the Conspectus of Chinese Modern History Course

Variable	major	number	mean	Standard Deviation	F	LSD
knowledge mastery	Literature and history (A)		4.454	0.619	3.089*	B<A,C,D
	Science and technology (B)	57	4.223	0.684		
	Economic management (C)	594	4.465	0.583		
	Arts (D)	46	4.516	0.547		
emotional motivation	Literature and history (A)	134	4.542	0.578	2.647*	B<A,C,D
	Science and technology (B)	57	4.459	0.557		
	Economic management (C)	594	4.611	0.511		
	Arts (D)	46	4.710	0.494		
behavioral guidance	Literature and history (A)	134	4.593	0.536	1.494 n.s.	
	Science and technology (B)	57	4.491	0.594		
	Economic management (C)	594	4.621	0.528		
	Arts (D)	46	4.699	0.552		
Overall Sense of gain	Literature and history (A)	134	4.526	0.525	2.843*	B<A,C,D
	Science and technology (B)	57	4.382	0.546		
	Economic management (C)	594	4.561	0.483		
	Arts (D)	46	4.635	0.461		

* p<0.05

2. analysis of the influencing factors of college students' sense of gain from the Conspectus of Chinese Modern History Course

2.1 Correlation analysis among various research variables

Firstly, the correlation between social support, family rendering and school teaching and "knowledge mastery", "emotional motivation", "action orientation" and "overall sense of gain" is analyzed. The results are shown in table 5, the total score of college students' sense of gain from the Conspectus of Chinese Modern History Course and its three dimensions are significantly positively correlated with social support, family rendering and school teaching.

Table 5 correlation analysis of college students' sense of gain from the Conspectus of Chinese Modern History Course and social support, family rendering and school teaching

	knowledge mastery	emotional motivation	behavioral guidance	Overall Sense of gain	School teaching	family rendering	Social support
knowledge mastery	1	.701**	.616**	.891**	.381**	.418**	.491**
emotional motivation	.701**	1	.767**	.910**	.430**	.453**	.579**
behavioral guidance	.616**	.767**	1	.873**	.498**	.615**	.682**
Overall Sense of gain	.891**	.910**	.873**	1	.484**	.548**	.646**
School teaching	.381**	.430**	.498**	.484**	1	.599**	.614**
family rendering	.418**	.453**	.615**	.548**	.599**	1	.695**
Social support	.491**	.579**	.682**	.646**	.614**	.695**	1

** P<0.01

2.2 Regression analysis of school teaching, family rendering and social support on the sense of gain

Stepwise multiple regression method is used to further analyze the correlation between school teaching, family rendering and social support on "knowledge mastery", "emotional motivation", "intention and action orientation" and "overall sense of gain". According to table 6, the three predictors "school teaching", "family rendering" and "social support" all have significant predictive power on "overall sense of gain". The multivariate correlation coefficient of the three predictors and the dependent variable of "overall sense of gain" is 0.665, the determination coefficient R² is 0.442, and the F value of the regression model integrity test is 217.971***. Therefore, the three predictors could effectively explain the variation of "overall sense of gain" of 44.2%. From the perspective of the predictive power of each variable, "social support" is the independent variable with the most predictive power for "overall sense of gain", and its explanatory variation is 41.7%. The second is "family rendering", with an explanatory variation of 1.9%. The third is "school teaching", which explains the variation of 0.6%. From the perspective of the standardized regression coefficient, the Beta values of the three prediction variables in the regression model are 0.476, 0.160 and 0.096, respectively. All positive values mean that their influences on the "overall sense of gain" are all positive.

On the dimension of knowledge mastery, the three predictive variables of "school teaching", "family rendering" and "social support" all had significant predictive power on "knowledge mastery". The multivariate correlation coefficient between the three predictive variables and the dependent variables of "overall sense of gain" is 0.508, the determination coefficient R² is 0.258, and the F value of the regression model integrity test is 95.716***. Therefore, the three predictive variables can effectively explain the variation of 25.8% of "knowledge mastery". In terms of the predictive power of each variable, the independent variable of "social support" is the strongest predictor of "knowledge mastery", and its explanatory variation is 24.1%. The second is "family rendering", with an explanatory variation of 1.2%. The third is "school teaching", which explained that the amount of variation is 0.5%. From the perspective of the standardized regression coefficient, the Beta values of the three prediction variables in the regression model are 0.351, 0.118 and 0.095, respectively. All positive values mean that their influences on "knowledge mastery" are all positive.

On the emotional motivation dimension, among the three predictive variables, there are two variables with significant predictive power for "emotional motivation", namely "social support" and "school teaching". The multivariate correlation coefficient between the two predictive variables and the dependent variables of "emotional motivation" is 0.586, the determination coefficient R² is 0.344, and the F value of the regression model integrity test is 216.677***. Therefore, the two predictive variables could effectively explain the 34.4% variation of "affective motivation". In terms of the predictive power of the two variables, the predictive power of "social support" to "emotional motivation" is higher than that of "school teaching", with an explanatory variation of 33.5%. The explanatory variation of "school instruction" is 0.9%. From the perspective of the standardized regression coefficient, the Beta values of the two prediction variables in the regression model are 0.505 and 0.119, respectively. Both positive values mean that their influences on "emotional

motivation" are both positive.

In terms of behavioral guidance, among the three predictive variables, there are two variables with significant predictive power for "behavioral guidance", namely "social support" and "family rendering". The multivariate correlation coefficient between the two predictors and the dependent variables of "behavioral guidance" is 0.710, the determination coefficient R² is 0.504, and the F value of the regression model integrity test is 420.579***. Therefore, the two predictors can effectively explain the 71.0% variation of "behavioral guidance". In terms of the predictive power of the two variables, the predictive power of "social support" is higher than that of "family rendering" (46.6%). The explanatory variation for "home rendering" is 3.8%. From the perspective of the standardized regression coefficient, the Beta values of the two prediction variables in the regression model are 0.494 and 0.272, respectively. Both positive values mean that their influences on "emotional motivation" are both positive.

Table 6 regression analysis of school teaching, family rendering and social support on the sense of gain

The dependent variable	The independent variables	Multivariate correlation coefficient	R ²	increment	F	Net value F	B	Beta
Overall Sense of gain	d						2.015	
	Social support	0.646	0.417	0.417	593.497***	593.497***	0.405	0.476
	family rendering	0.661	0.436	0.019	320.504***	28.106***	0.108	0.16
	School teaching	0.665	0.442	0.006	217.971***	7.709*	0.064	0.096
knowledge mastery	d	134	4.542	0.578			2.114	
	Social support	0.491	0.241	0.241	263.370***	263.37***	0.36	0.351
	family rendering	0.503	0.253	0.012	139.934***	12.761***	0.095	0.118
	School teaching	0.508	0.258	0.005	95.716***	5.695*	0.077	0.095
emotional motivation	d						2.199	
	Social support	0.579	0.335	0.335	416.984***	416.984***	0.457	0.505
	School teaching	0.586	0.344	0.009	216.677***	11.226*	0.085	0.119
behavioral guidance	d						1.754	
	Social support	0.682	0.466	0.466	722.764***	722.764***	0.455	0.494
	family rendering	0.71	0.504	0.038	420.579***	63.716***	0.198	0.272

***p<0.001

2.3 Model analysis of the influence of three factors on college students' sense of gain from the Conspectus of Chinese Modern History Course

Further, the structural equation model is used to verify and analyze the relationship between school teaching, family rendering and social support and the sense of gain. We run the path model on AMOS20.0, and the result is shown in figure 2. The influence degree can be reflected by the size of the corresponding path coefficient, the standardized partial regression coefficients of school teaching, family rendering and social support on the sense of gain are 0.10, 0.16 and 0.48, respectively. It shows that compared with school teaching and family rendering, social support has a positive impact on college students' sense of gain from the Conspectus of Chinese Modern History Course. By means of path analysis and comparing the results of multiple linear regression analysis, the correlation and influence between the variables of "school teaching", "family rendering" and "social support" as well as between them and college students' sense of gain from the Conspectus of Chinese Modern History Course are verified. The standardized regression equation is obtained as follows: college students' sense of gain from the Conspectus of Chinese Modern History Course = 0.48 * social support + 0.16 * family rendering + 0.10 * school teaching.

Figure 2 paths of "school teaching", "family rendering", "social support" and "sense of gain"

V. conclusions and Suggestions

1.conclusions

Through empirical research, this study explores the status quo and influencing factors of college students' sense of gain from the Conspectus of Chinese Modern History Course, and draws the following conclusions: First of all,

college students have a high overall level of sense of gain from the Conspectus of Chinese Modern History Course. In terms of the three dimensions of the sense of gain, the average score of the dimension of behavioral guidance is the highest, and the average score of the knowledge mastery is the lowest. In terms of demographic variables, there are no significant differences in gender and nationality, but there are some differences in specialty. Secondly, social support has a significant positive effect on college students' sense of gain from the Conspectus of Chinese Modern History Course. Thirdly, family rendering has a significant positive effect on college students' sense of gain from the Conspectus of Chinese Modern History Course. Specifically, family rendering has a positive effect on college students' knowledge mastery and behavioral guidance in the Conspectus of Chinese Modern History Course, and has no significant effect on emotional motivation. Finally, school teaching has a significant positive effect on college students' sense of gain from the Conspectus of Chinese Modern History Course, which is manifested in the positive effect of school teaching on college students' knowledge mastery and emotional motivation of the sense of gain from the Conspectus of Chinese Modern History Course, and the effect of attention to behavioral guidance is not significant.

2. Suggestions

2.1 Pay attention to relative weaknesses and professional differences.

In the three dimensions of the sense of gain, the average score of knowledge mastery is the lowest. The scores of students majoring in science and technology in the two dimensions of "knowledge mastery" and "emotional motivation" and the overall sense of gain are significantly lower than those majoring in literature and history, economics and management, and art. This reminds us that it is necessary to improve college students' knowledge of the Conspectus of Chinese Modern History Course. For college students

majoring in science and technology, more attention should be paid to them, and more in-depth education should be conducted on them based on various factors, so as to improve their sense of gain from the Conspectus of Chinese Modern History Course.

2.2 Social support must be constantly consolidated.

Great accomplishment in the current Chinese society inspires students' patriotism and national pride, to make the students understand the people's living standard and national development is synchronous, personal development and national development are complementary to each other, which can inspire the interests of students to learn the Conspectus of Chinese Modern History Course content, make students willingly and actively learning textbook knowledge, and eventually take it into action.

2.3 Emphasize the role of family education.

Family education should not only pay attention to the children's professional performance, but also pay attention to the children's ideological and political theory course learning and ideological and moral development status, and timely understand the children's ideological, psychological and physical health status, for the cultivation of moral, intellectual, physical, aesthetic, labor comprehensive development of compound talents to lay a foundation. to improve the ideological and political moral cultivation of parents, so as to better serve as a model for good children, to provide the necessary prerequisite for the formation of good character for children, so as to be conducive to children to accept the content of the Conspectus of Chinese Modern History Course in the future.

2.4 Strengthening school teaching.

It is necessary to continuously improve the professional quality, theoretical level and teaching ability of the

Conspectus of Chinese Modern History Course teachers. Under the premise of understanding the characteristics of students, innovate the teaching mode and choose the appropriate teaching method. The idea of "student-centered" education is applied to all aspects of the teaching of the Conspectus of Chinese Modern History Course. It is necessary to create a good classroom atmosphere and teacher-student relationship, so that the Conspectus of Chinese Modern History Course has both theoretical depth and warmth.

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